

Case Study

Role of Quantum Medicine in Fast Recovery of Dog after Acute Trauma Suffered in Traffic Accident

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Abstract

The case is about a dog injured in a car accident when it was urgently operated due to the appearance of blood in the abdomen. The condition was complicated by acute renal insufficiency, and a very quick recovery was achieved with a combination of classical therapy and quantum medicine.

Key words: Quantum medicine, BICOM, veterinary, hepatorenal syndrome**Introduction**

This case is about a three-year-old Bichon, which was injured in a traffic accident on 31 January 2025. The dog was admitted to veterinary clinic in a state of shock, with pale mucuous membranes, pronounced peripheral vasoconstriction, bleeding testicles. When admitted, the patient was in the lateral position, in the state of hypovolemic shock, tachycardic, tachypneic, with testicles outside the scrotum, external diffuse bleeding and hematomas on the back of the body, on the legs and stomach. Bloody fluid was aspirated by means of the peritoneal puncture. The x-ray imaging of the pelvis showed the fracture to the ilium and pubis. The blood test diagnosed anemia, showing the Hct value of 27.1. By means of the diagnostic laparotomy, hemoabdomen and uroabdomen were diagnosed. The findings revealed a complete destruction of the urethra distally from the prostate, without a possibility of being reconstructed, a complete rupture of the prostate, abdominal urethrostomy, as well as the castration due to the rupture of the scrotum, which was treated with tunika vaginalis. After the surgery, the urine production was reduced and the anuria protocol was applied. The recovery prognosis was uncertain. On 1 February 2025, there was a small amount of free fluid in the abdomen, the anemia persisted with the HCT level of 17.7, thrombocytopenia, leukocytosis, hypoalbuminemia, the albumin level of 17, increased levels of urea, creatinine, AST, ALT, and the blood transfusion was administered. On 2 February, the peripheral edema were present diffusely, and there was a small amount of free fluid in the abdomen; the dog vomitted, had anemia, with the HCT level of 19.6, thrombocytopenia, leukocytosis, hypoalbuminemia, the albumin level of 16, increased urea and creatinine levels.

On 3 February, there were diffuse peripheral edema, a small amount of free fluid in the abdomen, vomiting, and the blood transfusion was administered. On 4 February, the dog's condition was stable, and the administration of the prescribed therapy continued.

On 5 February, the dog's overall condition got worse, the peripheral edema were more pronounced, the amount of free fluid in the abdomen increased, the urination ceased. Then the quantum therapy was introduced. On 6 February, the level of urea was 30, and the creatinine level was 350, but the condition was a bit better. As of 5 May 2025 the quantum thera-

py was administered every day, twice a week, in the morning and in the evening during the period of three days. The therapy included the use of the BICOM optima and bbc2 devices for the diagnostic and therapeutic purposes, and involved the meridian programme for the kidneys and liver, the detoxication of the kidneys and liver, as well as the programmes which support the function of those organs given that the transaminase levels were elevated as an indicator of hepatorenal syndrome. On 6 February, the amount of free fluid in the abdomen reduced, the dog regained appetite, and nausea stopped. Diuresis was achieved even though no medicines were used.

On 7 February, the ultrasound imaging detected no free fluid in the abdomen.

On 8 February, according to the blood test findings, the urea level was 15.9, and the creatinine value was 225. The dog was discharged to continue treatment at home, but to keep coming to receive the therapy.

On 13 February, the results showed the urea level of 6.7, the creatinine level of 103, and the Hgb level of 108. So, again the quantum therapy was administered in order to improve the blood results. The vet at the clinic where the dog was treated believed that the anemia was the reaction of the organism to the blood transfusion administered to the dog. However, after the therapy the condition improved, and on 15 February, the Hgb level was 127.

When the dog's condition completely stabilised, the dog started going out, was able to move normally and run. The dog still has the uretostoma because so far no solution for the reconstruction has been found.

The colleague who owns the dog commented that every time she had been told that the dog would hardly make it through the night, it was me who helped him survive.

The introductory description of the case testifies of the important role of quantum medicine in the treatment of an acute injury of a dog and its fast recovery [1-3].

PODACI O PACIJENTU			
Ime životinje	Beki	Pol	M
Vrsta		Rasa	Bišon
Mikročip	688052000201565	Pasoš	RS 02145020
ANALIZA	REZULTAT	JEDINICA	
WBC	22,4	x10 ⁹ /L	
RBC	5,19	x10 ¹² /L	
HGB	124	g/L	
HCT	35,7	%	
MCV	68,8	fL	
MCH	23,9	pg	
MCHC	347	g/L	
PLT	648	x10 ⁹ /L	
LY	37,9	%	
MO	8,3	%	
EOS	1,0	%	
GR	52,8	%	
RDW	13,0	%	
PCT	0,47	%	
MPV	7,3	fL	
ANALIZA	REZULTAT	JEDINICA	
UREA	38,9	mmol/L	
CRE	348	μmol/L	
FOSFOR	2,1	mmol/L	
ALP	464	U/L	
ALT	158	U/L	
AST	-	U/L	
GGT	-	U/L	
BILIRUBIN UK.	6,8	μmol/L	
ALB	25	g/L	
UK.PROT	47	g/dl	
TRIGLICERIDI	-	mmol/l	
HOLESTEROL	-	mmol/L	
Na	149	mmol/L	
K	5,0	mmol/L	
GLUKOZA	4,9	mmol/L	
Ca	2,05	mmol/L	
KORTIZOL	-	nmol/L	
T4	-	mcg/dl	

U Beogradu, 6.2.2025.

PODACI O PACIJENTU			
Ime životinje	Natasa	Pol	Beki
Vrsta	1/25	Rasa	
Mikročip	688052000201565	Pasoš	
ANALIZA	REZULTAT		
WBC	20,0		
RBC	6,13		
HGB	153		
HCT	43,8		
MCV	71,5		
MCH	25,0		
MCHC	349		
PLT	539		
LY	17,5		
MO	3,9		
EOS	1,2		
GR	77,4		
RDW	14,8		
PCT	0,39		
MPV	7,3		
ANALIZA	REZULTAT		
UREA	15,9		
CRE	225		
FOSFOR	1,0		
ALP	385		
ALT	143		
AST	/		
GGT	/		
BILIRUBIN UK.	8,6		
ALB	29		
UK.PROT	55		
TRIGLICERIDI	/		
HOLESTEROL	/		
Na	152		
K	4,3		
GLUKOZA	5,1		
Ca	2,13		
KORTIZOL	/		
T4	/		

U Beogradu, 8.2.2025.

Conclusion

The combination of classical medicine and quantum medicine can speed up recovery even in acute conditions, as this case has shown.

References

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